

Problems seen in Zenodo, and DOI, provided by Datacite to Zenodo

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Abstract:

One of the platform for publication, Zenodo, as is found to be indexed in Openaire, and providing DOI(Digital Object Identifier) from Datacite, has few problems seen regarding the citations. In this paper, we shall attempt to discuss about them, as per author's profile.

Introduction:

Zenodo, as from it's website, talks about being a part of CERN, and talks same for it's storage capabilities. However, more then introducing Zenodo, we shall focus on our problems and discuss for possible solutions.

In the picture below, which is screenshot, of author's work, concerns about Numerical indexing, because to distinguish, among any two different topics, we need to have, at least two distinguish numbers as identifiers, when numbers are talked as identifiers. In "Cite all version?" section, we can see number 4940017, and in "Cite as" we can see number 4940018.

Thus, either topics would be of $(n+1)$ or $(n-1)$, for values of n provided either 4940017, or 4940018, problem would be seen in updating.

Beautiful Problem:

Regardless of two different numbers, when we access, then we arrive at same page. I don't know, if that is due to URL, webpages or such topics, because when we talk as mathematically,

$n+1 = n-1$ then, that would result $2=0$,

which is a contradiction, as two doesn't equals to zero.

Then comes question about numbers again.

I had mentioned few tweets about that topics in my twitter account with username arjundahalard [Twitter Profile of Arjun Dahal](#) , and that too shows about discussion of numbers, as we rely, and must have to rely, on basic principles of counting, to distinguish between any two topics.

Thus, when we would talk about numerical identification, new numbers would be needed, if any version of paper is uploaded. Even if we wouldn't provide new numbers then version 1, version 2, and such topics would be needed to keep our data, with updates.

Solutions:

I don't know, what would Zenodo do, to address two different numbers for same papers, but easiest solution would be, having two numbers for same paper or uploaded materials, which when accessed from any other link, would allow to access the link of published portion in Zenodo(as profile of individuals and their privacy) would play role, and that would be like as providing link, where any two numbers when accessed would open same page.

That would provide Zenodo to interact with third party websites, by allowing one value of n to be dependent or independent of DOI, where as due to same one value of n, materials would be indexed in DOI, and would be recognized by Digital Object Identifier(DOI).

That solution would seem bad, however, if we talk about two numbers, then, one number can be talked as original, and another can be talked for allowing for updates, which would reconcile with "Cite all versions?"

Actknowledgements:

My actknowledgements goes to doi.org, where some of DOI's provided by Zenodo couldn't be resolved, and all Registered agencies of DOI, as well as Zenodo, for publishing my works, with two numbers, which would be amazingly brilliant in computing, and web developing, but not in Mathematics, as 2 wouldn't be equal to zero.